

TNF α functions in an interconnected system with interleukin-1 β .

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While signaling in a cancer cell can be considered essentially binary with growth or survival an ultimate outcome, an immunologic system can be more complex, relating to transactions involving more than two cell types in the immune system, and decisions relating to gene expression in cells operating within an organism that possesses a dedicated immune system whose collective desired outcome, rather than cycling, growth or survival is protection of a host at the cellular level but involving integration of complex, non-binary multi-cellular circuits and use of specific immunologic ligands to signal infection, inflammation, or sickness. Accordingly, circuitry underlying the minimal components of an immunologic system may not necessarily be rationally ascertained, rather understood empirically as in during a clinical encounter. We describe here a minimal immunologic system containing the tumor necrosis factor alpha and interleukin-1 beta. A cellular system demonstrated strict relation between TNF alpha and interleukin-1 beta. Genetic manipulation of TNF alpha resulted in compensatory changes in interleukin-1 beta expression which were significant at the transcriptome level indicating essential interrelatedness of the innate immune immunologic effectors. Similarly, endogenous interleukin-1 beta was closely expressed with TNF in a basic transcriptional network in immune cells, and its expression appeared to support resistance in response to TNF-alpha inhibition using a monoclonal agent in humans with inflammatory and autoimmune disease.

Citations

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